

SEMANTIC RELATIONS BETWEEN PARTS OF AN OXYMORON

A.Saminov

filologiya fanlari

bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD).

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Аннотация

Ушбу мақолада nutqda ғайриодатий тушунча ёки фикр ифодалаш учун хизмат қилувчи оксюморон синтактик figurasini komponentlari o'rtasidagi ma'noviy munosabatlari yoritilgan.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются духовные отношения между компонентами оксюморонной синтаксической фигуры, служащей для выражения необычного понятия или мысли в речи.

Annotation

This article examines the spiritual relations between the components of an oxymoronic syntactic figure that serves to express an unusual concept or thought in speech.

Таянч сўз ва иборалар: оксюморон, ғайриодатий бирикма, синтактик қолип, бошқарув, битишув, мослашув, семантик муносабат.

Ключевые слова и фразы: оксюморон, необычное соединение, синтаксический модель, контроль, примычание, согласование, семантическое отношение.

Key words and phrases: oxymoron, unusual phrases, syntactic pattern, control, adhesion, adaptation, semantic relation.

In speech, we can observe that words that are connected in an unusual way, which are not compatible with each other in terms of their semantic relationship, come into contact. In this, the harmony of the syntactic relationship between words is broken. Formed using words connected in this way, speech is characterized by emotionality, emotionality, expressed using lexemes in which the creative (speaker) intended purpose-intention does not logically dictate each other.

As a result of the introduction of unusually concatenated words or sentence fragments into the relationship, a separate artistic image tool, a kind of stylistic figure, comes to the surface. This causes the speech to take on an expressive tone and become impressive. Unusual bonding can also be widely used in fine arts such as thirst, likeness, revitalization, intoxicity, as well as in the surfacing of the oxymorone (unusual compound) method.

In terms of the form of expression, there is syntactic valence between the parts of the oxymoron, which is considered a syntactic figure equivalent to a word combination and a sentence. True, among the components of oxymoron, the syntactic relation, as in lexical Valence, is expressed when one word is spoken, the other is embodied before our eyes, that is, when we write the word read, objects such as a book, a newspaper, a journal are not activated in our minds.

Among the components of oxyumorone, as in typical compounds, various semantic relationships are observed:

1. Predicative relation. In this, the possessive and the participle enter the syntactic relation, and the semantic connection comes to the surface: for example,

Oqsoq tek turmas,

Soqov – jim. (Maqol)

Oqshom cho'kib, keldi-ketdi uzilgach, uyda **ona-bolalar yolg'iz qolishdi.** (Jamila Ergasheva "Zulfizar" 2010)

2. An attributive relation-the semantic connection between a character and an object consists of a determinant-defined relation: for example,

Havo sovuq. Osmonda zahardek achchiq qor uchqunlari erinchoq kezadi. Ko'chalarni oynadek muz bosgan, mashinalar emaklagandek qo'rqa-pisa imillaydi. Nafas olsang, og'zinga **sovuq olov** kiritayotgandek bo'g'zingni achishtiradi. Odamlar toyg'onoqda yiqilib mayib bo'lmaslik uchun ehtiyotlab qadam bosadi. (O'.Hoshimov)

Muhabbat, ey **go'zal iztirob,**

Ko'chang kezdim sarson, dovdirab,

Yuzlarimga yuzlaring tirab,

Ko'zlarimni boylab qo'yding-ku!.. (Muhammad Yusuf)

3. The object relation is formed by the semantic connection between the complement and the complement. This situation occurs between something and action:qon tomchilaridan yorishmoq, baxtsizlik uchun kurashmoq.

Baxtsizlik uchun kurashish nima degani o'zi. Bu hamma narsadan voz kechish, hammasini unitish, befarqlik, loqaydlikka yuz tutish deganimi?.. Yoki qabohat, jirkanch tuyg'ular bilan oshno bo'lib yashashmi?.. Agar shunday bo'lsa siz bir umr **baxtsizlik uchun kurashib yashabsiz.** (N.Otaxonov)

Quyosh horib yiqildi,

tirqirab sizindi qoni,

uning **qon tomchilaridan yorishdi** Osmon. (Tursun Ali)

4. In the relative relation, however, a semantic connection is established between hol and Hollandi, resulting in the relationship between state and action:

Bu fikrni men sizga **tekinga sotdim**, falsafa daftaringizning bir chekkasiga qistirib qo'ying. (Tohir Malik "Shaytanat"), **Suyunganidan yig'layotipti**... Ammo-lekin qiz bola suyunganidan yig'lasa **yomon ham chiroyli yig'laydi-da.** (A.Qahhor "Tobutdan tovush")

5. The oppositional relation consists of an explanatory-annotated relation, in which the building material of the oxyumoron is made up of " ot+ot: Hofiz Zelixon Xongireyev kimligini bilmasam yurgan ekanman-da "o'qilonman", de-yeb kerilib. Haddingdan oshma, bola. Har ishning o'z hadisi bo'ladi. **Akademik o'g'ri.** O'g'rilikda unga teng keladiganini topish qiyin. Zelixon "akademik" o'g'ri, **Chuvrindi-Mahmudning** fojiali o'limidan keyin u ittifoqsizlik haqida ko'p o'ylardi. O'lim bilan yakunlanuvchi noaxillik sababini bilolmay garang edi. Pul talashishadi, desa, hammasi pulga ko'milib yotibdi.

Zohidning xayoli **Chuvrindi** kelguniga qadar shu muammolar bilan band bo'ldi. **Mahmud Esonov** ayni aytilgan vaqtda, bir daqiqa nari-beri qilmagan holda keldi. U bilan birga xonaga yoqimli atir hidi ham kirdi. **Chuvrindi** kun issiq bo'lishiga qaramay, oq-pushtiga moyil kostyum kiygan, qizil galstuk bog'lab olgan edi. Sochlarini silliq taragan, o'ng qo'lining

ko'rsatkich barmog'iga tilla uzuk taqqan odamni birov "**Chuvrindi**", deb chaqirsa, kulgili holat yuz berardi.

Chuvrindi bashang kiyingani bilan harakatida, qarashlarida, hol-ahvol so'rashayotganidagi ovozida kibr sezilmadi.

Toxir Malik is a true member of the Academy of Sciences, an academic lexeme in our first example, quoted from the story "Shayatinat"; a scholar, scholar, artist, sculptor, elected to membership of any academy, and so on. The title of is used in quality, the writer used the oxyumoron method using a lexeme of a positive meaning in relation to the thief Zelikhan. The lexeme "Chauvrindi" in the second example is annotated in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language as "an old, juldur-clad man; poor". Coincidentally, the nickname "Chuvrindi" is a reference to Mahmud's position at the time of his discovery. But as can be seen in the above sentence, Mahmud Esonov – "Chuvrindi" is embodied in the image of an incredibly rich person (hero). It can be seen from this that the "Chuvrindi" Mahmud formed the oxyumorone in the explanatory-annotated mold.

According to the syntactic mold, such constructions often consist of compounds in a determinant-defined relationship, with the meaning of the determinant negating the meaning of the logically identifiable or the meaning of the identifiable determinant.

In the oxyumoron method, the main logical meaning of the determinant is eliminated by the emotional meaning. For example: unusual compounds such as the shout of silence, quiet rebellion can be cited.

Shaftolirang olam nayza uchinda...

Dunyolari yolg'on, men o'ldim chindan...

Barno Bonu, sizni **achchiq sog'indim**. (Rauf Parfi)

The bitter word used in the combination "bitter miss" in the above passage of speech is used to denote the quality of material objects. And in this combination, as a sign of the word Miss, which has lost its main meaning and has been used in an emotional sense, has become a methodological tool that expresses the author's subjective attitude towards what is being described.

In the following passage of speech, however, the combination of "shouted silence" manifests itself in the manner of an unusual syntactic device:

Kezadir bulutlar boshim ustida.

Havo dim.

Baqirgan sukunat.

Sukunat – vujudlarga, miyalarga, sanchilgan igna! (R.Parfi)

In this, the poet revealed the edges of his own meaning through the shouting silence, silence – oxyumorons like a pricked needle. Silence – (Arabic سكونت-silence, silence; 1. Lack of any sound; 2. Silence, silence), losing the positive meaning of the word silence by tying the words of the needle, and shouting, exaggerating the negative meaning in the words of the needle. The poet equated the word silence to the needle and vividly expressed the effect of silence on the human psyche.

In such combinations, words that semantically negate one of the other serve to exaggerate the author's positive or negative attitude to an event-event. As another example: taking the combination "Horror Is Beautiful", "The Word" "Horror" serves to strengthen the positive meaning, losing its main meaning. "Horror" (Arabic دهشت – surprise, surprise. Finally level fear, danger, panic.) despite the negative connotation being an expressive word, the

influence of the epithet further adds to the positive connotation edge of the word “beautiful”. For example: - Ish yurishmasa, **atala tish sindiradi**, degan maqol bor. Sizning ishingiz shunaqa bo‘libdi. (Toxir Malik. “Shaytanat”)

In speech, certain parts of such unusual combinations are attached with a methodological goal and context requirement, and in them the advantage of moving away from each other in content is clearly visible, rather than converging. For example: shirin o‘lim, qora nur, muzlagan faryod, g‘arib baxtiyorlik, otashin muzlar, baxtiyor gadolar kabi.

Oxyumoron is also a syntactic-stylistic figure, which increases artistic representativeness, expressiveness in the expression of something, phenomenon and reality as a manifestation of other stylistic tools. With the presence of opposing meaningful concepts in a combination of words or sentences formed using the oxyumoron method, as well as generating a new unexpected expressiveness, a strong image acquires in speech.

It is known that the importance of pictorial means in improving serjeality and specific dyeing in the expression of various images and events is incomparable, making the language of a work of art perfect, impressive. The occurrence of an unusual connection between two lexical units is calculated from the problems of lexical Stylistics.

In general, in compounds formed by the oxyumorone method, the semantic relationship is manifested in the same manifestations as above. Situations like this indicate that the semantic and methodological possibilities of expression of our language are endless, Without Borders.

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